

Improving Food Processing Labor Skills in Laos through Cooperative Training (CT)

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Laos #2 (2021)

At a glance:

Based on our case study survey, the majority of the factories said that most common vocational skills development (VSD) programmes did not contribute to alleviating skills needs. In-employment programmes address employers' needs better than pre-employment ones.¹

According to our survey:

- Small to medium food processing factories struggled to find qualified, skilled or experienced employees.
- Recruitment is based on availability of interested local people, and qualified people prefer to work in larger and more stable factories.
- This necessitates provision of specific in-house training or on the job training to newly recruited staff to overcome skill shortages.
- The perception of the value of training programmes is very different among the factories surveyed considering the demands of growth and transformation.
- As these in-house training schemes have been deployed without any collaboration and cooperation among the factories or with local training institutions, these in-house trained employees can barely adapt to the growth and transformation of their respective factories with respect to changing products and technology.

Consequently, this policy brief recommends that:

Training institutions offering Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programmes should strongly and effectively collaborate with industry to identify their specific skill training needs and cooperatively implement practically orientated training, e.g. Cooperative Training (CT) or Competence Based Training (CBT) or others.²

Food processing industry situation:

It is a nationwide challenge to develop a skilled labor market both in the short- and long-term perspective. The food processing industry in Laos is growing with the number of small and medium firms increasing based on market demand for products such as canned corn, coffee, dry fruit and local food. This has especially been the case during the Covid-19 outbreak. However, there are few qualified and skilled workers in the labor market to draw on to support the food industry, and these require higher pay than factories can afford.

This lack of qualified and skilled workers, and the respective potential for factory growth or transformation of value chains is a key limiting factor for the food industry. Apart from processed coffee products, other food processing often fails to reach the safety or quality standards required for exporting or even to compete among domestic products.

¹ The case studies are part of the “Skills for Industry” project conducted to explore the contribution of TVET programmes to industrial growth and transformation of manufacturing companies. Prior to the case studies, a contextual analysis and survey of companies were conducted, based on which a first policy brief was published here: <https://phzh.ch/en/Research/skills-for-industry/publications/>

² For example see: Vacki Wangyeng, Sobsan Utakrit and Nattakant Utakrit (2018). Multidimensional Perspectives on Readiness in Dual Cooperative Training at Lao-German Technical College for Heavy Equipment Program. 5th International Conference on Business and Industrial Research (ICBIR), Bangkok, Thailand.

Almost all food processing products have not fulfilled the conditions or benchmarks certified by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) or good manufacturing practice (GMP). Despite the government strategy to develop the labor market to meet the specific qualitative and quantitative needs of industry, the curriculum developed by existing public and private educational or training institutions has not satisfied these needs. There are few education or training institutes offering courses related to food processing in Laos. Many graduates of universities or vocational schools have not been trained with food industry-specific practical knowledge, and further compounding the issue do not wish to work in this sector. Most factories recruit locally from less qualified employees with a secondary school education.

Low cost, low investment labor force of the food processing industry in Lao PDR:

Our case study indicates that factories tend to hire villagers living around the factories as it is more convenient. This was mentioned by the production manager of a salt factory during the first phase interview:

“General workers should be villagers in Khoksaat Village as they are local people and it is convenient for them to go to work. If we choose people far away from the factory it may be difficult for the transportation. Normally, general workers are the family group working as contractors, they work with good attitude, patient ... and the factory paid them depending on task quantity and quality (paid every 15 days)”.

Investment in labor is key to industry growth and transformation, yet most companies chose to employ unskilled employees at low salary cost. Based on our company survey from phase 1, for 44 Food Processing Companies (see Figure 1), general workers, operators and technicians were likely to have only a basic education (85, 70 and 90 percent respectively). Only administrators were more likely

to have a Diploma and Higher Education Level (90 percent). Qualified, skilled or experienced employees demand higher wages as mentioned by the factory manager during the interview:

“Absolutely, our factory would like to find excellent and experienced employees. However, nobody with high qualification want to work with us as we could not pay them with a higher wage around 2-3 million Kip per month, thus we hired general workers instead.”

With the rates of qualifications illustrated in Figure 1, the growth and transformation of industry is handicapped. Moreover, the food processing industry faced difficult problems in pre-training staff so as to meet factory production targets. Last but not least, we estimate that, in some factories, about 2-3 employees resigned during or within 1 or 2 weeks after the training (per training cohort), which is a challenge for factory recruitment.

Figure 1 Workforce education level of Food Processing industry in Laos

Training in food processing:

To reflect the needs of food processing industries and to better adapt to these needs, industries should cooperate and collaborate with TVET institutions e.g. to set up Cooperative Training (CT) between two parties (stakeholders). In doing this, students or trainees gain the technical skills and knowledge from TVET institutions and learn work attitudes and gain experience within industries as to meet the current demands of the respective businesses.

Industries benefit from a well-trained, productive and loyal workforce while reducing recruitment and training costs. After finishing training programs, factories can identify and select new employees by working skill assessments.

According to our case study (6 food processing factories), before entering work in a factory, new employees received pre-training in order to familiarize them with their tasks. Approximately 67 and 42 percent of conducted trainings for MSE³ and HSE⁴ respectively are introductory training focused on hygiene and safety regulations. In-employment training within the company accounted for 18 and 30 percent for MSE and HSE, respectively. Only 3 and 12 percent of MSE and HSE obtain pre-employment training with formal and non-formal TVET as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Percentage comparison of training programmes for new recruitment

Many companies provided training by themselves. According to their perception, the in-house training provided may be more efficient than training from TVET institutions. After all, the production processes are not complicated as mentioned during an interview with an HR manager:

“We train new staffs with the in house training or work directly with real machine or equipment by focusing on the production process. The first training’s content focus on the hygiene, safety, etc., since we are in food production industry”.

³ Middle-level skilled employees
⁴ Higher-level skilled employees

“As the factory operation system is not so complicated, we provide trainings 2-3 times to our staffs so that later they could work in real factory. In addition, local people know the factory since their childhood thus they could observe our staffs working and later they could apply for a job here”.

Some factories have their own permanent trainers who can provide on-the-job training to staff. This is a reason that they do not need to collaborate with government training organizations, as mentioned by a restaurant manager during the interview:

“We prefer on-job-training because we already have our own recipe, so the trainers can train our staff according to our recipe. Staff may graduate from vocational schools, but working in our restaurant they have to use the restaurant’s recipe and style, so on-job-training will be preferred”.

Cooperative training in practice:

Cooperative training plays a fundamental role in enhancing the efficiency and quality of employment oriented vocational education and training in order to better meet the social and labour market needs of the growing economy in Lao PDR. The CT programme has been implemented in TVET flagship colleges with more than 80 companies participating and a CT service centre has also been established in the Lao National Chamber of Commerce and Industry. The integration of major economic sectors and key enterprises in TVET is indispensable and has to be seen as one key factor to ensure the envisaged economic growth.

The potential benefits of CT to industry:

- Reduced training costs: Since the training of the vocational learner is shared with TVET institutes, the industries receive vocational learners who already have some employability skills and occupational knowledge and can contribute to the enterprise’s productive processes.

- **Secure supply of qualified staff:** Due to in-company training, the industries have the possibility to train vocational learners according to their specific occupational needs. Permanent supervision by technical experts helps industries to prepare the vocational learners for their future roles as professionals in the same enterprises.
- **Higher productivity:** After an initial investment, the enterprises are expected to benefit from the vocational learners in terms of additional productivity and increased profit.
- **Lower recruitment costs:** The observation of vocational learners in real work condition facilitates recruitment and reduces the costs of recruiting and retraining. Since the industries already know the vocational learners, in particular their working and productivity level, there is a lower risk of hiring the “wrong person”.
- **Increased loyalty of vocational learners:** By providing a decent work environment to protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, in particular women, and those in precarious employment (target 8.8 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, 2015), industries have the possibility to increase loyalty of vocational learners, thereby reducing the risk of high turnover.
- **Better enterprise image:** Offering vocational training increases the enterprises’ reputation as Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) conscientious industries. This can have a positive impact on the industries’ brands as well as on their attractiveness as employers.

This policy brief recommends applying CT to the food processing industry through cooperation between the respective industries and vocational institution.

Recommendations:

To improve the quality of employee working skills, there is a need to:

1. Cooperatively create a master plan on human resource development through CT with TVET (including private sector executives)
2. Jointly organize workshops to determine training courses by TVET institutions and companies
3. Cooperatively identify specific human resource needs (concerned companies and TVET institutions)
4. Cooperatively implement associated training programmes both in TVET institutions and industry, such as the Dual-Cooperative Training programmes implemented by the German development agency, GIZ (2019)
5. Cooperatively organize follow-up programmes for trainees while working in the industry concerned
6. Jointly organize workshops to disseminate the training outcomes and sharing experiences (TVET, concerned industries and LNCCI)

Sources:

- GIZ (2021) Vocational education in Lao PDR. Accessed on 7 July 2021: <https://www.giz.de/en/worldwide/26261.html>
- UN (2015) Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. United Nations General Assembly. Accessed on 7 July 2021: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.html>

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